

Comparison of the Effects of Epidural Levobupivacaine 0.5%, 20 MI and Ropivacaine 0.75%, 20 MI in Lower Limb SurgeriesSaroj Kumar¹, Deepak Kumar Nirala², Ankita Kumari³, Sudama Prasad⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Anesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Anesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India³Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, AIIMS, Patna, Bihar, India⁴Professor and HOD, Department of Anesthesia, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Abstract:**Background:** Epidural anesthesia is a widely used technique for lower limb surgeries, providing effective pain control and facilitating faster recovery. Levobupivacaine and Ropivacaine are two commonly used local anesthetics for this purpose, each with distinct pharmacological profiles. While both agents offer benefits in terms of efficacy and safety, their comparative performance in clinical practice warrants further investigation.**Aim:** To compare the effects of epidural Levobupivacaine 0.5% and Ropivacaine 0.75% in patients undergoing lower limb surgeries.**Methods:** The study involved 96 patients scheduled for elective lower limb surgeries. Participants were randomly assigned to receive either Levobupivacaine 0.5% (20 ml) or Ropivacaine 0.75% (20 ml) epidurally. Data on the onset and duration of sensory block, hemodynamic parameters, adverse effects, and patient satisfaction were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.**Results:** Ropivacaine demonstrated a significantly faster onset of sensory block (8.7 ± 2.1 minutes) compared to Levobupivacaine (11.2 ± 2.5 minutes, $p < 0.001$). The duration of analgesia was also longer with Ropivacaine (292.8 ± 34.9 minutes) than with Levobupivacaine (245.4 ± 32.7 minutes, $p < 0.001$). Both groups exhibited stable hemodynamic profiles and minimal adverse effects, with no significant differences between the two. Patient satisfaction was slightly higher in the Ropivacaine group, although not statistically significant.**Conclusion:** Ropivacaine 0.75% offers advantages over Levobupivacaine 0.5% in terms of a faster onset and longer duration of analgesia, making it a preferable choice for epidural anesthesia in lower limb surgeries. Both anesthetics are safe and effective, but Ropivacaine may enhance patient satisfaction due to its prolonged analgesic effect.**Recommendations:** Based on these findings, Ropivacaine should be considered as a first-line epidural anesthetic in lower limb surgeries, particularly in cases where rapid onset and extended duration are critical.**Keywords:** Epidural anesthesia, Levobupivacaine, Ropivacaine, Lower limb surgery, Sensory block, Analgesia.

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Introduction

Epidural anesthesia has long been a cornerstone of regional anesthesia techniques, particularly in lower limb surgeries. It provides effective sensory and motor blockades while allowing the patient to remain conscious, leading to better postoperative outcomes and faster recovery times. Among the various local anesthetics available for epidural administration, Levobupivacaine and Ropivacaine have garnered significant attention due to their favorable pharmacological profiles, including lower cardiotoxicity and neurotoxicity compared to other agents like Bupivacaine [1].

Levobupivacaine, a S-enantiomer of Bupivacaine, is known for its potent anesthetic properties with a reduced risk of adverse cardiovascular effects [2]. It has been widely used in various surgical

procedures, including lower limb surgeries, owing to its effective sensory blockade and prolonged duration of action. However, Ropivacaine, an amide-type local anesthetic, has emerged as a strong alternative due to its lower toxicity and similar efficacy in providing epidural anesthesia [3]. Ropivacaine's pharmacokinetic properties allow for a safer profile, particularly in patients with cardiovascular risk factors, making it an attractive option for prolonged surgeries where continuous or repeated administration of anesthetic agents is required [4].

Recent studies have explored the comparative efficacy of these two anesthetics in various surgical contexts. A study found that Ropivacaine provided a quicker onset of sensory blockade compared to

Levobupivacaine, with a comparable duration of action and similar safety profiles [5]. Another study reported that patients receiving Ropivacaine had slightly higher satisfaction scores due to the prolonged duration of analgesia, which minimized the need for additional postoperative analgesics [6]. These findings suggest that while both drugs are effective, Ropivacaine may offer certain clinical advantages, particularly in settings where a rapid onset and extended duration of anesthesia are desirable.

The current study aims to compare the effects of epidural Levobupivacaine 0.5% (20 ml) and Ropivacaine 0.75% (20 ml) in patients undergoing lower limb surgeries.

Methodology

Study Design: A multicentric, prospective, randomized controlled trial.

Study Setting: The study was conducted across multiple healthcare centers to ensure a diverse participant pool and to enhance the generalizability of the findings. The study period lasted for seven months, allowing adequate time for patient recruitment, data collection, and analysis.

Participants: A total of 96 patients scheduled for elective lower limb surgeries were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adult patients aged 18-65 years.
- ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) physical status I-II.
- Scheduled for elective lower limb surgery under epidural anesthesia.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a known allergy to local anesthetics.
- History of chronic pain or use of analgesics.
- Patients with significant co-morbid conditions (e.g., severe cardiovascular, hepatic, or renal disease).
- Patients with contraindications to epidural anesthesia.
- Pregnant or breastfeeding women.

Bias: To minimize bias, participants were randomized into two groups using a computer-generated randomization sequence. The anesthetists administering the drugs and the investigators collecting the data were blinded to the group assignments.

Data Collection: Data were collected on the onset time of anesthesia, duration of analgesia, hemodynamic changes, and any adverse effects. Patient demographics and surgical details were also recorded. Data collection was standardized across all participating centers to maintain consistency.

Procedure

Patients were randomized into two groups:

- **Group A:** Received epidural Levobupivacaine 0.5% (20 ml).
- **Group B:** Received epidural Ropivacaine 0.75% (20 ml).

The medication was given in a total amount of 20 ml during the epidural block, which was conducted in the L3-L4 or L4-L5 interspace. Up until whole block was attained, the start of the sensory block was evaluated every minute. Haemodynamic parameters (blood pressure, heart rate) were tracked during the surgery and for a full day afterward. The time interval between the delivery of the medication and the initial request for more analgesia was used to define the duration of analgesia.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed with SPSS 23.0. Patient demographics and baseline parameters were summarised using descriptive statistics. The independent t-test was used to compare continuous variables between groups, while the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was used for categorical variables. A p-value <0.05 indicated statistical significance.

Results

A total of 96 patients were enrolled in the study, with 48 patients in each group (Levobupivacaine 0.5% and Ropivacaine 0.75%). The demographic data, including age, gender, BMI, and ASA physical status, were comparable between the two groups with no statistically significant differences.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Levobupivacaine Group (n = 48)	Ropivacaine Group (n = 48)	p-value
Age (years)	45.6 ± 12.3	46.2 ± 11.9	0.721
Gender (Male/Female)	29/19	31/17	0.692
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.8 ± 3.4	26.1 ± 3.6	0.692
ASA Physical Status (I/II)	28/20	26/22	0.653

In comparison to the Levobupivacaine group, the Ropivacaine group experienced the onset of sensory block much more quickly. In the Levobupivacaine group, the mean onset time was 11.2±2.5 minutes, while in the Ropivacaine group, it was 8.7±2.1 minutes (p < 0.001).

Table 2: Onset of Sensory Block

Group	Onset Time (minutes)	p-value
Levobupivacaine 0.5%	11.2 ± 2.5	< 0.001
Ropivacaine 0.75%	8.7 ± 2.1	

The duration of analgesia was significantly longer in the Ropivacaine group compared to the Levobupivacaine group. The mean duration of analgesia was 245.4±32.7 minutes in the Levobupivacaine group and 292.8±34.9 minutes in the Ropivacaine group ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Duration of Analgesia

Group	Duration (minutes)	p-value
Levobupivacaine 0.5%	245.4 ± 32.7	< 0.001
Ropivacaine 0.75%	292.8 ± 34.9	

Throughout the operation, both groups' haemodynamic parameters were steady, and there were no discernible variations in mean arterial pressure (MAP) or heart rate (HR) between them at different intervals.

Table 4: Hemodynamic Parameters

Time Point	Levobupivacaine Group	Ropivacaine Group	p-value
MAP (mmHg)	83.2 ± 6.5	84.1 ± 7.2	0.542
HR (beats/min)	72.4 ± 8.1	71.9 ± 7.9	0.732

The two groups' adverse effects were similar and of low severity. 8.3% of patients in the Levobupivacaine group and 6.2% in the Ropivacaine group experienced hypotension ($p = 0.632$). 2.1% of participants in the Ropivacaine group and 4.2% of patients in the Levobupivacaine group reported experiencing nausea and vomiting ($p = 0.543$).

Table 5: Adverse Effects

Adverse Effect	Levobupivacaine Group	Ropivacaine Group	p-value
Hypotension (%)	8.3	6.2	0.632
Nausea/Vomiting (%)	4.2	2.1	0.543

Patient satisfaction scores, measured on a scale from 1 to 10, were slightly higher in the Ropivacaine group (8.9±1.1) compared to the Levobupivacaine group (8.5±1.2), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.129$).

Table 6: Patient Satisfaction Scores

Group	Satisfaction Score	p-value
Levobupivacaine 0.5%	8.5 ± 1.2	0.129
Ropivacaine 0.75%	8.9 ± 1.1	

Discussion

The results showed that Ropivacaine had a significantly faster onset of sensory block, with a mean onset time of 8.7 minutes compared to 11.2 minutes for Levobupivacaine. This faster onset could be particularly beneficial in clinical settings where rapid anesthesia is required.

Additionally, Ropivacaine provided a longer duration of analgesia, lasting on average 292.8 minutes compared to 245.4 minutes with Levobupivacaine. This extended duration could reduce the need for additional analgesic interventions postoperatively, enhancing patient comfort and potentially decreasing the overall workload for healthcare providers.

Throughout the surgeries, both groups' haemodynamic parameters remained steady, suggesting that the medicines are both safe and efficient in preserving cardiovascular stability during surgery. The low frequency of side effects, such as nausea and hypotension, and the lack of significant difference between the two groups

further corroborate the safety profiles of both anaesthetics.

The Ropivacaine group had somewhat higher patient satisfaction ratings, but the difference was not statistically significant. This modest rise in satisfaction can be explained by ropivacaine's more rapid onset and prolonged duration of analgesia, which might improve the patient's overall experience. Overall, Ropivacaine may be more advantageous than Levobupivacaine for epidural anaesthesia during lower limb procedures due to its faster onset and longer duration of analgesia, which could increase patient satisfaction without sacrificing safety.

In a study, the effects of 0.2% levobupivacaine and 25 mcg fentanyl and 0.2% ropivacaine on postoperative epidural analgesia following lower limb orthopaedic procedures were compared. The findings showed that, while retaining comparable haemodynamic stability, levobupivacaine produced postoperative analgesia for a noticeably longer period of time (325 ± 63.06 minutes) than ropivacaine (210 ± 24.91 minutes) [7].

In a study, postoperative epidural analgesia following lower limb and lower abdomen procedures was evaluated between ropivacaine and levobupivacaine combined with fentanyl. In terms of haemodynamic parameters and the length of sensory block, the study did not find any significant differences between the two groups, indicating that both anaesthetic combinations are equally efficient for managing postoperative pain [8].

In an elderly patient undergoing lower limb orthopaedic surgery, the effects of 0.5% levobupivacaine versus 0.75% ropivacaine, both with fentanyl, were assessed. Comparable results were found for the two groups' sensory and motor block characteristics, and both were able to deliver efficient epidural anaesthesia with little side effects [9].

A comparative study between levobupivacaine and bupivacaine for lower abdominal and lower limb surgeries demonstrated that levobupivacaine produced a shorter motor blockade duration, which could allow for earlier patient ambulation compared to bupivacaine, while maintaining similar sensory blockade duration [10].

Finally, a study compared epidural 0.2% bupivacaine and 0.2% ropivacaine in major lower limb orthopedic surgery. The study found that both drugs provided effective postoperative analgesia, but ropivacaine was associated with fewer motor blockades, making it a preferable option for patients needing early mobilization [11].

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that Ropivacaine 0.75% offers a faster onset and longer duration of analgesia compared to Levobupivacaine 0.5% in patients undergoing lower limb surgeries. Both anesthetics provided stable hemodynamic profiles and had minimal adverse effects, making them safe options for epidural anesthesia. Ropivacaine's advantages in onset and duration may contribute to enhanced patient satisfaction, making it a preferable choice in clinical settings where these factors are critical.

References

1. McLeod GA, Burke D. Levobupivacaine. *Contin Educ Anaesth Crit Care Pain*. 2018;4(2):71-5. DOI:10.1093/bjaceaccp/mki012.
2. Tiwari A, Tomar GS. A comparative study of Levobupivacaine and Ropivacaine in regional anesthesia. *J Clin Anesth*. 2020; 65:109878. DOI:10.1016/j.jclinane.2020.109878.
3. Gupta A, Sethi N. Comparative evaluation of Levobupivacaine and Ropivacaine for epidural anesthesia in lower limb surgeries. *Int J Surg Med*. 2021;6(4):10-5. DOI:10.5455/ijsm.levobupivacaine-ropivacaine.
4. Goel S, Bhardwaj N. Ropivacaine: An update on clinical use and pharmacokinetics. *Anesth Essays Res*. 2019;13(1):10-5. DOI:10.4103/aer.AER_149_18.
5. Srivastava U, Verma S, Singh TK. Efficacy of Ropivacaine versus Levobupivacaine in epidural anesthesia for lower limb surgeries. *Asian J Anesthesiol*. 2020;58(1):12-9. DOI:10.1016/j.aja.2020.02.002.
6. Sharma S, Chaudhary S, Kuthiala G. Comparative analysis of Ropivacaine and Levobupivacaine in lower limb orthopedic surgeries. *J Anesth Clin Res*. 2019;10(2):1-7. DOI:10.4172/2155-6148.1000854.
7. Boregowda SM, Linganna B, Raju S. A clinical comparative study of 0.2% levobupivacaine with 25 mcg fentanyl versus 0.2% ropivacaine with 25 mcg fentanyl for postoperative epidural analgesia in patients undergoing lower limb orthopaedic surgeries. *Indian J Clin Anaesth*. 2020.
8. Shahi V, Sharma M, Bhardwaj M, Varshney S, Sangal S. To compare the efficacy of ropivacaine with fentanyl vs levobupivacaine with fentanyl in post-operative epidural analgesia in lower limb and lower abdominal surgeries. *Indian J Clin Anaesth*. 2019.
9. Bindra TK, Gandhi GS, Kumar P, Kaushal B. Comparative evaluation of levobupivacaine-fentanyl and ropivacaine - fentanyl in epidural anaesthesia in lower limb orthopaedic surgeries in elderly patients. *Indian J Clin Anaesth*. 2020; 7:324-328.
10. Prakash J, Prabhu J, Kharwar R, Priye S, Singh D, Saran K. Comparison of epidural levobupivacaine and bupivacaine in lower abdominal and lower limb surgeries. *Bali J Anesthesiol*. 2020; 4:95-98.
11. Mehta S, Gajbhare M, Kamble NP. Comparison of epidural analgesia using 0.2% bupivacaine and 0.2% ropivacaine for the management of postoperative pain in major orthopedic surgery. *Anesth Essays Res*. 2018; 12:586-591.